

Supporting Information

The nature of the active sites on Ni/CeO₂ catalysts for methane conversions

Pablo G. Lustemberg,^{1,2,†} Zhongtian Mao^{3,†}, Agustín Salcedo,^{4,5} Beatriz Irigoyen,^{4,5} M. Verónica Ganduglia-Pirovano^{1*} and Charles T. Campbell^{3*}

¹Instituto de Catálisis y Petroleoquímica (ICP-CSIC), 28049 Madrid, Spain

²Instituto de Física Rosario (IFIR-CONICET) and Universidad Nacional de Rosario (UNR), S2000EKF Rosario, Santa Fe, Argentina

³Department of Chemistry, University of Washington, Seattle, Washington 98195-1700, USA

⁴Universidad de Buenos Aires (UBA), Facultad de Ingeniería, Departamento de Ingeniería Química, Ciudad Universitaria, C1428EGA Buenos Aires, Argentina

⁵Instituto de Tecnologías de Hidrógeno y Energías Sostenibles (ITHES, CONICET-UBA), Ciudad Universitaria, C1428EGA Buenos Aires, Argentina

* Corresponding authors: Charles T. Campbell: charliec@uw.edu
M. Verónica Ganduglia-Pirovano: vgp@icp.csic.es

[†] These authors have contributed equally to this work.

Models and Computational Details

The extended metallic Ni(111), Co(0001) and Pt(111) surfaces were modeled as previously reported, the two former ones by Liu et al.¹ and the latter by Lustemberg et al.². The CeO₂(111) oxide support was modeled with the calculated ceria bulk equilibrium lattice constant of 5.485 Å. Table S1 indicates the size of the unit cell used for each Ni_n-CeO₂ model catalyst and the number of CeO₂ (O–Ce–O) tri-layers of the ceria slab. All Ni_n-CeO₂ models used in this work are shown in Figure S1 where the most representative distances are indicated in pm. In all surface models, consecutive slabs were separated by at least a 12 Å-thick vacuum layer to avoid interaction between the slabs and their periodic images.

Monkhorst-Pack grids³ have been used for *k*-point sampling as listed in Table S1. All atoms in the two (one) bottom layers of Ni₁-CeO₂ (Ni₄, Ni₁₃ and Ni₅₊₁.step) were kept fixed at their optimized bulk-truncated positions during geometry optimization, whereas the rest of the atoms were allowed to fully relax. The integral heat of adsorption of Ni gas atoms forming Ni_n clusters on the CeO₂(111) support was calculated at 0 K as $E_{\text{ads}} = -1/n [E(\text{Ni}_n\text{-CeO}_2) - E(\text{CeO}_2) - n \cdot E(\text{Ni}_{\text{atom}})]$ where $E(\text{Ni}_n\text{-CeO}_2)$

and $E(\text{CeO}_2)$ are the total energies of the $\text{Ni}_n\text{-CeO}_2(111)$ and $\text{CeO}_2(111)$ surfaces, and $E(\text{Ni}_{\text{atom}})$ is that of a gas-phase Ni^0 atom in the d^9s^1 configuration, calculated with a $(12 \times 11 \times 16) \text{ \AA}^3$ periodic cell and the Γ -point. The lattice parameter of bulk fcc Ni was optimized (Ni_{bulk} : 3.48 \AA , DFT+D3), using a Monkhorst-Pack grid with $(15 \times 15 \times 15)$ k-point sampling of the Brillouin zone, and the heat (enthalpy) of sublimation of bulk Ni (bulk cohesive energy) was calculated to be $\Delta H_{\text{sub,Ni}}^{\text{calc}} = 518 \text{ kJ/mol}$. These are in good agreement with prior results.^{4,5}

The adsorption energy of methane was calculated according to the following equation for the example of the dissociative adsorption on the $\text{Ni}_n/\text{CeO}_2(111)$ system: $E_{\text{ads}} = E[(\text{CH}_3+\text{H})/\text{Ni}_n\text{-CeO}_2(111)] - E[\text{Ni}_n\text{-CeO}_2(111)] - E[\text{CH}_{4\text{gas}}]$, where $E[(\text{CH}_3+\text{H})/\text{Ni}_n\text{-CeO}_2(111)]$ is the total energy of the methyl and hydrogen species co-adsorbed on the surface, $E[\text{Ni}_n\text{-CeO}_2(111)]$ is the total energy of the surface without the adsorbate, $E[\text{CH}_{4\text{gas}}]$ is the energy of the methane molecule in gas phase.

To locate transition state (TS) structures, we employed the climbing image nudged elastic band method (CI-NEB)⁶ with nine images for each reaction pathway. For all the TS reported in this work, we have found only one imaginary frequency, and the full geometry optimizations starting from its back and forward nearest configurations (along the reaction path) ended in a non-dissociated and dissociated state, respectively.

In the calculated potential energy profiles, the energy barrier, $E_{\text{Barrier}} = E_{\text{TS}} - E_{\text{IS}}$, equals the difference between the energy of the transition state, E_{TS} , and the initial (molecularly chemisorbed) state, E_{IS} , whereas the effective or apparent energy barrier is given by the energy of the transition state, E_{TS} , referenced to gas-phase CH_4 and the clean surface.

Catalyst	Unit cell periodicity	k-pts mesh	Number of ceria trilayers
Ni(111)	3 × 3	5 × 5 × 1	5
Ni₁-CeO₂	2 × 2	3 × 3 × 1	4
Ni₄-CeO₂	3 × 3	2 × 2 × 1	2
Ni₁₃-CeO₂			
Ni_{5+1.step}-CeO₂	5 × 3	1 × 2 × 1	
Ni_{4+1.step}-CeO₂			
Ni_{3.step}-CeO₂			
Ni_{3.trimer.step}-CeO₂			
Ni_{3+1.step}.CeO₂			
Ni_{4.step}.CeO₂			
Ni_{5.step}.CeO₂			

Table S1. Computational setup employed for each $\text{Ni}_n\text{-CeO}_2$ model catalyst.

The energies in Figure S1 show that the Ni_{5.step} cluster alone is 23 kJ/mol of Ni (or 115 kJ/mol total) less stable than the Ni_{4+1.step} structure, so that the Ni_{5.step} cluster alone would spontaneously decompose into the Ni_{4+1.step} structure. This explains why we needed to study the Ni_{5+1.step} structure in order to study a Ni₅ cluster at a step. The added Ni monomer at the step (which is separate from the Ni₅ cluster) simply maintains the stability of the cluster against dissociation, but did not have any apparent effects on the reaction of the Ni₅ step-edge cluster with methane (see below).

System	E _{IS}	E _{FS}	E _{FS} -E _{FS} [Metal]	E _{TS}		E _{Barrier}		ΔE _{TS} =
				Predicted	Calculated	Predicted	Calculated	ΔE _{Barrier}
Ni(111)	-25.0	-33.6	0.0	77.8	61.4	102.7	86.4	-16.3
Ni ₁ -CeO ₂ (111)	-39.4	-41.3	-7.7	72.0	44.2	111.4	83.6	-27.8
Ni _{4.2D} -CeO ₂ (111)	-23.0	-99.8	-66.2	32.6	-9.6	55.7	13.4	-42.2
Ni _{13.i} -CeO ₂ (111)	-42.2	-11.5	22.1	92.2	-9.6	134.4	32.6	-101.8
Ni _{13.t} -CeO ₂ (111)	-34.6	-32.6	1.0	77.8	0.0	112.3	34.6	-77.8
Ni _{3.step} -CeO ₂	-46.1	-47.4	-13.8	70.1	67.6	116.2	113.7	-2.5
Ni _{5+1.step} -CeO ₂	-78.7	-129.6	-96.0	-13.4	-70.1	65.3	8.6	-56.7

Table S2. Calculated (no ZPE correction) energies (in kJ/mol) for the initial, E_{IS}, final, E_{FS}, and transition states, E_{TS}, for the CH₄(gas) → CH₃ + H reaction on Ni_n (n = 1, 4, 13) on CeO₂(111) terraces and Ni₃ and Ni₅+N₁ (Ni₅₊₁) at a <110>-type step, as well as the (111) surface. Ni_{13.t} and Ni_{13.i} denote dissociation on a terrace and at an interface site of the Ni₁₃-CeO₂ system, respectively. All energies are relative to CH₄ in the gas phase and the corresponding clean systems. The predicted E_{TS} values correspond to the values obtained using the linear scaling relation E_{TS} = (0.67 E_{FS} + 1.04) for the actual calculated final state, E_{FS}. The predicted E_{Barrier} values correspond to the activation energy barrier calculated as the energy difference between the predicted energy of the transition state and the calculated energy of the initial state. The model catalysts whose E_{TS} energy is less than zero is related to the fact that on them, CH₄ binds relatively strongly, so that if the barrier for the first H abstraction from the chemisorbed CH₄ molecule is sufficiently low, E_{TS} will be negative when referenced to gas-phase CH₄ and the clean surface.

Figure S2. Lowest energy paths for the $\text{CH}_4 \rightarrow \text{CH}_3 + \text{H}$ reaction over the Ni/CeO₂ systems studied. For the Ni₅ pyramid at a $\langle 110 \rangle$ ceria step, the lowest energy path involves cooperative interactions between a metal cation and an O center, where hydrogen binds to a surface oxygen and methyl is adsorbed at the apex of the Ni₅ pyramid (no ZPE correction). The dissociation products correspond to stable chemisorbed states geometrically close to the corresponding transition state (TS), which we show in Figure S3. For the Ni₁₃-CeO₂ system the lowest energy states of CH₃ and H bound to Ni₁₃ are shown in Figure S6.

Figure S3. Initial state (IS), transition state (TS), and final state (FS) for the $\text{CH}_4 \rightarrow \text{CH}_3 + \text{H}$ reaction on the ceria-supported Ni_{5+1} aggregate at a $\langle 110 \rangle$ -type step and the Ni_1 , Ni_4 , 2D and Ni_{13} clusters on $\text{CeO}_2(111)$ terraces. Selected interatomic distances (in pm) are indicated.

Figure S4. Binding of CH₃ on the ceria-supported Ni₅₊₁ aggregate at a <110>-type step and the Ni₁, Ni₄, 2D and Ni₁₃ clusters on CeO₂(111) terraces. Selected interatomic distances (in pm) are indicated. Adsorption energies are relative to CH₃ in the gas phase and the corresponding methyl-free systems.

Figure S5 Adsorption of atomic H on various systems (kJ/mol wrt $\frac{1}{2}$ H₂). The number of Ce³⁺ correspond to the changes upon hydrogen adsorption (Δ Ce³⁺). For the case of adsorption on a Ni²⁺ adatom (b) with initially 2×Ce³⁺, the H/Ni₁-CeO₂ system has 1 Ce³⁺ and thus Δ Ce³⁺= -1.

System	H Binding Energy (kJ/mol wrt $\frac{1}{2}$ H ₂)	
	O–H	Ni–H
Ni(111)	-	-60.7
(a) CeO ₂ (111)	-118.1	-
(b-c) Ni ₁ -CeO ₂	-96.70	+17.0
(d) Ni ₄ -CeO ₂	-	-116.9
(e) Ni ₁₃ .i-CeO ₂	-	-54.1
(f) Ni ₁₃ .t-CeO ₂	-	-27.4
(g) O.t.step-CeO ₂	-123.0	-
(h) O.s.step-CeO ₂	-144.1	-
(i) Ni ₅₊₁ .step-CeO ₂	-162.4	-

Table S3. Hydrogen binding energy on selected systems (see Figure S5). Ni₁₃.t and Ni₁₃.i denote adsorption on a terrace and at an interface site of the Ni₁₃-CeO₂ system, respectively, and O.t. step-CeO₂ and O.s. step-CeO₂ denote adsorption on an O atom at a terrace and at the step edge of the <110> step-CeO₂ system, respectively.

Figure S6. Lowest energy states for the adsorbed CH₃+H products of the first hydrogen abstraction from CH₄ on the Ni₁₃ clusters supported on CeO₂(111) terraces. Selected interatomic distances (in pm) are indicated.

System M		CH ₄ .gas	CH ₄ /M-CeO ₂	CH ₄ /M-CeO ₂ -CH ₄ .gas
Ni ₅₊₁ .step	C	4.0076	4.1291	0.12
	H	1.0033	0.9340	-0.07
	H	0.9871	1.0147	0.03
	H	0.9845	0.9371	-0.05
	H	0.9884	0.9452	-0.04
	Total	7.9709	7.9601	-0.01
Ni ₁	C	4.0076	3.9129	-0.09
	H	1.0033	0.9943	-0.01
	H	0.9871	1.0393	0.05
	H	0.9845	1.0533	0.07
	H	0.9884	1.0049	0.02
	Total	7.9709	8.0047	0.03
Ni ₄ .2D	C	4.0076	4.1650	0.16
	H	1.0033	0.9304	-0.07
	H	0.9871	0.9965	0.01
	H	0.9845	0.9465	-0.04
	H	0.9884	0.9364	-0.05
	Total	7.9709	7.9748	0.00
Ni ₁₃ .i	C	4.0076	4.1440	0.14
	H	1.0033	0.9161	-0.09
	H	0.9871	0.9384	-0.05
	H	0.9845	0.9625	-0.02
	H	0.9884	1.0179	0.03
	Total	7.9709	7.9789	0.01
Ni ₁₃ .t	C	4.0076	4.1166	0.11
	H	1.0033	0.9432	-0.06
	H	0.9871	0.9975	0.01
	H	0.9845	0.9722	-0.01
	H	0.9884	0.9446	-0.04
	Total	7.9709	7.9741	0.00

Table S4. Bader charges (Q, in |e|) for a CH₄ molecule in the gas phase (CH₄.gas) and molecularly adsorbed (CH₄/system-CeO₂) on the ceria-supported Ni₅₊₁ aggregate at a <110>-type step and the Ni₁, Ni₄.2D and Ni₁₃ clusters on CeO₂(111) terraces. Ni₁₃.t and Ni₁₃.i denote adsorption on a terrace and at an interface site of the Ni₁₃-CeO₂ system, respectively. Bader charge differences (CH₄/system-CeO₂-CH₄.gas) are also listed.

System	Band	Empty States			Difference of Empty States	
		M.gas	M.CeO ₂	CH ₄ /M.CeO ₂	M.CeO ₂ -M.gas	CH ₄ /M.CeO ₂ -M.CeO ₂
Ni ₅₊₁ .step	dz ²	0.13	0.16	0.07	0.03	-0.09
	dxy	0.15	0.31	0.16	0.16	-0.15
	dxz	0.25	0.18	0.23	-0.07	0.05
	dyz	0.15	0.15	0.18	0.00	0.03
	dx ² -y ²	0.22	0.07	0.07	-0.15	0.00
	dtotal	0.90	0.87	0.71	-0.03	-0.16
Ni ₁	dz ²	0.48	0.00	0.00	-0.48	0.00
	dxy	0.03	0.26	0.31	0.23	0.05
	dxz	0.09	0.28	0.24	0.19	-0.04
	dyz	0.11	0.28	0.32	0.17	0.04
	dx ² -y ²	0.44	0.26	0.25	-0.18	-0.01
	dtotal	1.16	1.08	1.11	-0.08	0.03

Table S5. Integration of the projected density of states onto the d-states of the Ni atom at apex of the Ni₅ pyramid of the Ni₅₊₁.step system within the 0 (E_F) to +1.0 eV (+0.50 eV for Ni₁) energy interval. M.gas corresponds to the free-standing Ni₅₊₁ aggregate resulting from the removal of the CeO₂ support from Ni₅₊₁.step-CeO₂, without further geometry optimization. M.CeO₂ corresponds to the results for the Ni₅₊₁.step-CeO₂ system, and CH₄/M-CeO₂ to those for the CH₄ adsorption on Ni₅₊₁.step-CeO₂.

System M	Atom	M-CeO ₂	M.gas	M-CeO ₂ -M.gas	CH ₄ /M-CeO ₂	CH ₄ /M-CeO ₂ - M-CeO ₂
Ni_{5+1.step}	Ni1	15.8217	15.9263	-0.10	15.6392	-0.18
	Ni2	15.4463	16.0075	-0.56	15.5135	0.07
	Ni3	15.4218	16.0122	-0.59	15.4410	0.02
	Ni4	15.3345	15.9672	-0.63	15.4091	0.07
	Ni5	15.4586	15.9683	-0.51	15.5161	0.06
	Ni6	15.2655	16.1185	-0.85	15.3067	0.04
	Total	92.7484	96.0000	-3.25	92.8256	0.08
Ni₁	Ni1	15.0559	16.0000	-0.94	15.0302	-0.03
Ni_{4.2D}	Ni1	15.6472	16.1172	-0.47	15.7271	0.08
	Ni2	15.7281	16.1123	-0.38	15.7405	0.01
	Ni3	15.7752	15.8868	-0.11	15.6519	-0.12
	Ni4	15.7896	15.8838	-0.09	15.7701	-0.02
	Total	62.9401	64.0001	-1.06	62.8896	-0.05
Ni_{13.i}	Ni1	15.7760	15.9926	-0.22	15.7653	-0.01
	Ni2	15.7686	15.9945	-0.23	15.7778	0.01
	Ni3	15.7584	16.0759	-0.32	15.7583	0.00
	Ni4	15.6206	15.8241	-0.20	15.6629	0.04
	Ni5	15.7271	15.9925	-0.27	15.7089	-0.02
	Ni6	15.7570	15.9845	-0.23	15.7143	-0.04
	Ni7	15.7783	16.0961	-0.32	15.7462	-0.03
	Ni8	15.4933	16.0833	-0.59	15.6272	0.13
	Ni9	15.7255	16.0713	-0.35	15.7182	-0.01
	Ni10	16.0614	15.9764	0.08	16.0527	-0.01
	Ni11	16.0312	15.9647	0.07	16.0160	-0.02
	Ni12	16.0361	15.9785	0.06	16.0445	0.01
	Ni13	15.9869	15.9656	0.02	15.9949	0.01
	Total	205.5204	208.0000	-2.48	205.5872	0.07
Ni_{13.t}	Ni1	15.7760	15.9926	-0.22	15.8074	0.03
	Ni2	15.7686	15.9945	-0.23	15.7851	0.02
	Ni3	15.7584	16.0759	-0.32	15.7692	0.01
	Ni4	15.6206	15.8241	-0.20	15.6622	0.04
	Ni5	15.7271	15.9925	-0.27	15.7292	0.00
	Ni6	15.7570	15.9845	-0.23	15.7608	0.00
	Ni7	15.7783	16.0961	-0.32	15.7943	0.02
	Ni8	15.4933	16.0833	-0.59	15.4587	-0.03
	Ni9	15.7255	16.0713	-0.35	15.7384	0.01
	Ni10	16.0614	15.9764	0.08	16.0543	-0.01
	Ni11	16.0312	15.9647	0.07	16.0269	0.00
	Ni12	16.0361	15.9785	0.06	16.0468	0.01
	Ni13	15.9869	15.9656	0.02	15.8968	-0.09
	Total	205.5204	208.0000	-2.48	205.5301	0.01

Table S6. Bader charges (Q, in |e|) of the Ni atoms of a ceria-supported Ni₅₊₁ aggregate at a <110>-type step and of Ni₁, Ni_{4.2D} and Ni₁₃ clusters on CeO₂(111) terraces (M-CeO₂), see Figure S1. For Ni, 16 electrons (3p⁶, 3d⁸, 4s²) were considered as valence. The charges upon adsorption of CH₄ is also listed. The atom on which CH₄ adsorbs is indicated in bold. Ni_{13.t} and Ni_{13.i} denotes adsorption on a terrace and at an interface site of the Ni₁₃-CeO₂ system, respectively. M.gas corresponds to the free-standing systems resulting from the removal of the CeO₂ support from M-CeO₂, without further geometry optimization. Bader charge differences (M-CeO₂-M.gas and CH₄/M-CeO₂- M-CeO₂) are also listed.

Figure S7. Projected density of states (PDOS) onto the d-states of the Ni atom at the apex of the Ni_5 pyramid of the Ni_{5+1} .step system. The energy zero is the Fermi level (E_F). The green, red, orange, violet and blue filled curves are the corresponding d_{z^2} , d_{xy} , $d_{x^2-y^2}$, d_{xz} , and d_{yz} projected density of states, respectively. a-e) show the results for a free-standing Ni_{5+1} aggregate resulting from the removal of the CeO_2 support from Ni_{5+1} .step- CeO_2 , without further geometry optimization, f-j) corresponds to the results for the Ni_{5+1} .step- CeO_2 system, and k-o) shows those for the CH_4 adsorption on Ni_{5+1} .step- CeO_2 . The empty states close to E_F are highlighted.

Figure S8. Projected density of states (PDOS) onto the d-states of a Ni atom on a CeO₂(111) terrace. The energy zero is the Fermi level (E_F). The green, red, orange, violet and blue filled curves are the corresponding d_{z^2} , d_{xy} , $d_{x^2-y^2}$, d_{xz} , and d_{yz} projected density of states, respectively. a-e) show the results for a free-standing Ni₁ aggregate resulting from the removal of the CeO₂ support from Ni₁-CeO₂, without further geometry optimization, f-j) corresponds to the results for the Ni₁-CeO₂ system, and k-o) shows those for the CH₄ adsorption on Ni₁-CeO₂. The empty states close to E_F are highlighted.

We further note that for many of the systems in the original set in ref. ⁷, CH₄ is barely or not adsorbed and thus $E_{\text{Barrier}} (E_{\text{TS}} - E_{\text{IS}}) = E_{\text{TS}}$ and $E_{\text{Reaction}} (E_{\text{FS}} - E_{\text{IS}}) = E_{\text{FS}}$. However, this is not true for some of the metal-CeO₂ systems (nor for IrO₂(110) and Pd(101)), for which the binding of the initial state is substantial with one C-H bond partially activated, as discussed above. Figure S9 displays the activation energy as a function of the reaction energy for selected systems. The comparison between the best linear fit for the E_{Barrier} vs. E_{Reaction} data corresponding to the Ni₄.2D, Pt₄.2D, Co₄.2D, and Ni₁₃ clusters on terraces and Ni₅₊₁ at steps and that for the E_{TS} vs. E_{FS} in Figure 3 of the main text, indicates that 60% of the slope of the E_{TS} vs. E_{FS} regression line is due to a “true” Brønsted relation, and 40% is due to the fact that the final state energy tracks to some extent the initial state energy. This 40% is due to the simple fact that metal sites that strongly bind one small C/H containing adsorbate also tend to bind other C/H containing adsorbates strongly.

Figure S9. Brønsted relation between the calculated activation barrier (E_{Barrier}) and reaction energy (E_{Reaction}) for the surface-stabilized pathway in methane dissociation on a variety of materials. The purple (+) and yellow (x) symbols are for IrO₂(110) and Pd(101) presented in ref. ^{8,9} and ref. ¹⁰, respectively. The green, red and blue symbols correspond to the values for M₁ atoms and M₄ clusters (M= Pt, Co, Ni) on the CeO₂(111), respectively. Values for the extended Pt(111), Co(0001) and Ni(111) surfaces, as in ref. ², as well as on the Ni₁₃ clusters on terraces and Ni₃ and Ni₅₊₁ at steps are shown. The blue line is the best linear fit for the data corresponding to the Ni₄.2D, Pt₄.2D, Co₄.2D, and Ni₁₃ clusters on terraces and Ni₅₊₁ at steps.

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